

PYRIDINE COMPLEXES OF METALLIC PERCHLORATES. PART IV.
DISSOCIATION PRESSURES AND PRESSURE—COMPOSITION
ISOTHERMALS OF COMPLEXES OF PERCHLORATES
OF COBALT AND NICKEL

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The dissociation pressures of the pyridine complexes of cobalt perchlorate and that of nickel perchlorate have been measured at different temperatures, and the isothermal curves showing pressures against the number of molecules of pyridine per molecule of cobalt or nickel perchlorate have been determined at 50°. From these results it has been proved that in the solid state only two stable complexes for each salt, namely $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{Py}$, $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Py}$; $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{Py}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Py}$, are formed (where Py denotes pyridine). The heats of dissociation of the highest pyridinated complexes of cobalt and nickel only have been calculated from the plots of $\log_{10} p$ against $10^6/T$ graphs and these values are 12,617 cal. for $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{Py}$ and 12,290 cal. for $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{Py}$ per g. mol. of pyridine respectively, indicating that the cobalt complex is slightly more stable than the corresponding nickel complex.

By measurement of dissociation pressures of copper pyridine perchlorates at different temperatures and a study of the isothermals of copper perchlorate-pyridine system at 30° and 50°, Sinha and Ray (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, **44**, 790) have proved that in the solid phase only two stable complexes, viz., $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{Py}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Py}$ are formed and that their heats of dissociation are 8,450 and 11,640 cal. per g. mol. of pyridine respectively. It was considered worthwhile to extend the study to the case of the pyridine complexes of other bivalent metallic perchlorates to ascertain, if any, the influence of the cation on the behaviour and stability of these complexes. Corresponding complexes of cobalt and nickel have been chosen in the first instance, as these two elements occur in the Periodic Table just before copper and have the values of ionic radii approaching that of the bivalent copper ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Perchlorate of cobalt and nickel were prepared by the action of 60% perchloric acid solution on the carbonates of the corresponding metal, suspended in water, and crystallising them out. Pyridine complexes of these perchlorates were obtained from these by dissolving the dry salts in excess of boiling pyridine, cooling and filtering out the complexes (Ray and Sinha, this *Journal*, 1943, **20**, 33).

The apparatus used and the method of procedure for the measurement of dissociation pressure was the same as that described in the case of copper perchlorate system (*loc. cit.*). The results obtained are summarised in Table I and graphically represented in Fig. 1. The logarithms of pressures are also plotted against the reciprocals of the absolute temperature, and the rectilinear graphs obtained are shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

FIG. 1

TABLE I

*Temperature-pressure values.*System : $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6/4 \text{ Py}$.

Temp.	...	50°	59.8°	67.0°	72.1°	80.4°	85.5°	87.0°	89.6°	90.3°	91.0°
p (mm Hg)	...	26.5	47.2	74.6	95.2	143.2	183.3	208.5	234.9	256.3	263.1
$10^6/T$ (°K)	...	3096	3025	2941	2898	2830	2789	2778	2758	2753	2747
$\text{Log}_{10} p$	...	1.423	1.674	1.873	1.979	2.155	2.260	2.319	2.371	2.409	2.420

Mean value of the heat of dissociation (calc. from graph) = 12,517 cal. per g. mol. of pyridine.

System : $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6/4 \text{ Py}$.

Temp.	...	36.5°	40.3°	50.0°	59.2°	71.2°	74.3°	81.0°
p (mm Hg)	...	11.2	14.14	24.4	43.2	83.1	94.8	136.1
$10^6/T$ (°K)	...	3231	3192	3096	3010	2905	2879	2825
$\text{Log}_{10} p$	...	1.049	1.149	1.387	1.636	1.920	1.977	2.134

Mean value of the heat of dissociation (calc. from graph) = 12,290 cal. per g. mol. of pyridine.

Determination of Isothermals.—It consisted mainly of the measurement of loss in the weight of pyridine with its gradual removal at a fixed temperature and the simultaneous determination of pressure. For this purpose, an oblong bulb containing the complex and a little of excess of pyridine was attached to the main apparatus through a mercury-sealed ground-glass vacuum joint. The loss in weight of the bulb with its progressive removal with the help of a pump was determined by detaching it and weighing it each time and noting the dissociation pressure before the bulb was detached. Thus, a series of values of dissociation pressures with the corresponding values of weights were obtained.

The isothermals were determined at 50°. At the end of the experiment the contents of the bulb were quantitatively transferred to a measuring flask and analysed for both the pyridine and the metallic salt. From the results of analysis and the loss in the weight, the number of molecules of pyridine per molecule of the salt was calculated. The results obtained are plotted in Fig. 3.

DISCUSSION

It is evident from the results of measurements of vapour pressure at different temperatures, that under the conditions of the study, the only stable solid complexes formed between pyridine and the perchlorates of cobalt and nickel are $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{Py}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Py}$ for the former, and $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{Py}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Py}$ for the latter. It may be noted, however, that indications for the existence of a complex for cobalt and another for nickel, each having a dissociation pressure higher than the hexapyridinated complexes of the perchlorates, have been obtained, but as the dissociation pressure curves of these are not reproducible, and especially as no breaks in the isothermal curves at any stoichiometric compositions of both the systems have been observed, these have been left out. It appears that loose adsorption compounds between pyridine and the solid complexes are formed. This conclusion is further supported by the smooth bends

in the isothermal curves for both the systems round about the sudden drops in the pressure values near the ratios 6Py and 4Py to each molecule of the perchlorate.

FIG. 3
Curve marked by circles refers to Ni complex
crosses " Co "

The order of the stability observed in the case of copper, cobalt and nickel perchlorates seems to be reverse of the order proposed by Irving and Williams (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3202) for those ions in solution; the anomaly may be due to the difference in the lattice energies of the crystals of the perchlorates and the pyridine complexes which more than compensates for the effect of the second ionisation potential and the ionic radii of the bivalent ion, but unless data on lattice energies are available, it is difficult to generalise.

In the case of the corresponding amines, it was observed by Salvadori (*Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 19) that $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{NH}_3$ lost NH_3 in air and was hydrolysed by water; no data however, were recorded of the heat of dissociation. In the case of $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{NH}_3$, Ephraim (*Ber.*, 1910, 48, 3103) studied the dissociation pressure between 210° and 225° and by applying Nernst's approximation formula calculated the heat of dissociation to be 19,100 cal. per g. mol. of NH_3 . Thus, it would appear that the ammine is more stable than the corresponding pyridine complex. This is in agreement with the observations of Larson (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1934, A169, 207) on the ammoniates of silver ion and of Bjerrum (*Chem. Rev.*, 1950, 46, 381) on the ammoniates of mercuric ion, if we can assume that the lattice energies of the ammine and pyridine complexes of the perchlorates are comparable.